

THE ROLE OF STORY-BASED LEARNING APPROACH IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. This article gives insightful information about the effectiveness of using story-based approach, storytelling in teaching English language. There are underlined the benefits of implementation of story-based approach in EFL classes.

Key words: story-based approach, storytelling, EFL class, motivation, learner's need, imagination, critical thinking, skill and competence.

РОЛЬ ПОДХОДА К ОБУЧЕНИЮ НА ОСНОВЕ ИСТОРИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. В данной статье дана познавательная информация об эффективности использования сторителлингового подхода, сторителлинга в обучении английскому языку. Подчеркнуты преимущества внедрения сюжетного подхода на занятиях по английскому языку.

Ключевые слова: основанный на рассказе подход, рассказывание историй, урок английского языка, мотивация, потребность учащегося, воображение, критическое мышление, навыки и компетентность.

INTRODUCTION

Children love stories. Stories are magic, they can create other worlds, emotions, ideas and make the everyday seem incredible. They can teach us empathy and take us on terrific journeys. They can make us laugh, cry, jump with fright and then comfort us with a happy ending. From a very young age we learn how to enjoy a story both for pleasure and to help us make sense of the world and ourselves. In this article I'll look at why stories are important for ESL students and I'll share some simple story-based activities that can be adapted for different ages and abilities.

Growing up, children listen to fairy-tales which provide an accessible way to communicate important messages to children in a playful, simple manner. Younger minds make connections between the fairy-tale world and real-life situations, which helps them develop problem-solving skills. Put another way, stories make it easier for children to receive and process information. Storytelling as a teaching method is thus a highly effective tool for building up new knowledge and learning a variety of 21st-century skills.

A story-based learning approach moves children into the world of imagination while acquiring new skills, which simplifies the educational process and makes it more effortless.

Storytelling is a teaching method which helps young learners solve given problems and tasks in a playful way and creates constructive and creative comprehension of the given matter.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Presented with a storyline, children perceive the learning process more easily and effortlessly. In this way, the acquisition of new knowledge and skills is veiled in a game, making it attractive to children who don't even realize they're learning.

Benefits of story-based lessons

The storytelling technique is known to be one of the most effective teaching strategies. The main benefits of the storytelling technique are: high motivation and active participation, a boost of creativity, cooperation between children, deepening the understanding of a subject, and an increase in attention span.

Storytelling motivates children to be active participants in the construction of the meaning of the story. Thus they feel that they can have a greater impact on the process and on the results of the assignment, and therefore are more motivated in its execution.

Furthermore, the storytelling learning approach helps children develop literacy, imagination, creation and critical thinking skills more effectively.

This approach supports the development of children's metacognitive skills, awareness, and also promotes self-regulated learning and a positive attitude towards making mistakes and self-critique. We have a curriculum full of educational and exciting lessons with various levels of complexity for different age groups.

A story-based approach helps to engage young learners with the content, boost their motivation and introduce them to the concepts of robotics and coding in a playful way. The storytelling technique involved in each lesson is an important activity for children for multiple reasons: it helps increase motivation, enhances language use, and boosts memory and attentiveness. Storytelling in learning also builds personal emotional attachment, creates positive associations, and durable, long-term learning benefits.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Additionally, this way of forming tasks makes what might be a difficult subject such as programming more digestible. Learning something via storytelling helps children remember outcomes and the process of execution better, as well as having an in-depth understanding.

In the ESL classroom stories have a special place and value. Students can listen to the sounds and rhythms of English just as native speakers will have done to acquire their first language. Students can identify vocabulary and expressions that they have learnt or heard regularly and see them in use. Frequent telling can help them to learn new phrases and expressions with the correct emotional resonance. Storytelling with participation uses experiential learning to ask about what is happening to the characters and what they should do next, or offers a student the chance to be that character and hear/say their words in a true context.

Storytelling brings language learning alive and creates a participatory and immersive experience that allows Young Learners to enjoy hearing the language in a dynamic, sometimes stylistic and entertaining way. Participation using key vocabulary and phrases can create an awareness of rhythm and structure. This atmosphere of play and creative expression creates an appetite for more similar experiences. Students who have enjoyed storytelling in class often ask for more stories and also feel motivated and encouraged to create and tell, act out or illustrate their own stories in a variety of ways.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, Storytelling also helps students to enjoy and be aware of intonation and tone of voice, natural sounding expressions and phrases as well as interaction between native speakers. For older YLs they offer the opportunity to retell, rephrase, enact or summarize what they've heard, to rewrite the story or to create their own as a group or individual. Stories

offer everyone a chance to enjoy language and discover new worlds, new words and new things about themselves.

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